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**REINVENTING MATURE PRODUCTS THROUGH COLORS,
MATERIALS, AND FINISHES**

Chih-Feng Li * / Jin-Dean Cheng / Lin-Lin Chen

Department of Industrial and Commercial Design, National Taiwan University of Science and
Technology

* D9610105@mail.ntust.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we review the role of colors, materials and finishes (CMF) in reinventing the notebook computer (NB) product, and report two case studies of CMF practices in two large NB manufacturers in Taiwan. By in-depth interviews of CMF professionals and product designers, we documented and analyzed the role of CMF in NB product development process, contents and sources of CMF database, services provided by CMF professionals, development of new CMF, and interaction between designers, engineers and CMF professionals.

Keywords: Material, Processing, CMF.

INTRODUCTION

In the current market filled with abundant product choices, consumers are no longer satisfied by functions and utilities offered by a product. Fulfilling the aesthetic, meaning, and emotional needs of consumers has become important in product design. Traditionally, product designers focused on satisfying these intangible needs via product forms. Over the last decade, the attention has gradually turned to the importance of materials in influencing consumers' experience of aesthetics, meanings and emotions of a product (Ashby 2003, Karana et al. 2008, van Kesteren 2008, Pedgley 2009).

As Ashby (2003) described, perceptions of a product goes beyond the selection of materials alone; the processing of the materials is also important. In the industry, this is manipulated by a combination of colors, materials, and finishes (or "CMF"), which deal with the exterior skin of the product. Although CMF has gained importance in the industry, there

have been few case studies reported in the literature about the role of CMF related technologies in product design. To this end, Dell'Era et al. (2010) reports two case studies on Italian furniture companies—Kartell and Luceplan—about how these companies combine innovation in product meanings with innovation on materials, surface treatments, and production processes to create competitive advantage in a highly saturated market. Figure 1 shows the Louis Ghost Chair designed by Philippe Starck for Kartell. The designer's concept is successfully interpreted through Kartell's injection molding technology by producing the entire chair using transparent polycarbonate in a single mold.

Figure 1. Louis Ghost Chair by Philippe Starck for Kartell

Similar to furniture, notebook computer (NB) is also a mature product with mostly standardized components. CMF capability is recognized by the NB manufacturers as critical, because it holds potentials to create profits by re-inventing the product appearance, but could also have great impacts on the production processes and costs. The objective is therefore to develop innovative CMF that adds values to a product while keeping manufacturing costs under control. Furthermore, CMF capability is seen to represent the overall competitiveness of a manufacturer—the precise combination of colors,

materials, and finishes is a testimony to the technology sophistication of the manufacturer, as well as the strength of its supporting supply networks.

During the last few years, many NB manufacturers in Taiwan have begun to establish their in-house CMF databases. In this paper, we will report on case studies of CMF practices in two large NB manufacturers. By in-depth interviews of CMF professionals and product designers, we seek to document and analyze the role of CMF in NB product development process, contents and sources of CMF database, services provided by CMF professionals, development of new CMF, and interaction between designers, engineers and CMF professionals.

CMF FOR NOTEBOOK COMPUTERS

Notebook computers have been produced and sold commercially since 1975. It is a mature product with a stable system architecture and standardized components. To differentiate among the many NB brands and models on the market, one of the most effective ways is to create innovative expressions in the exterior skins of notebook computers through combination of colors, materials, and finishes. Many well known brands already make use of CMF to create their signature look and feel, such as Apple's use of anodized aluminum in its series of products.

CMF treatments on notebook computers range from the more common lacquer coating on plastic part, to in-mold decoration (IMD) technology, and metal surface treatment. Figures 2, 3, 4 show example notebook computers with different CMF treatments: ABS plastic with lacquer coating (Figure 2), ABS plastic with in-mold rolling (IMR) (Figure 3), and aluminum alloy with brushing (Figure 4). By combining two or more processing steps, more sophisticated expressions can be created—for example, by combining brushing and laser pattern cutting on aluminum alloy plate (Figure 5). By developing an advanced IMD technology, called imprint 3D, which creates complicated 3-dimensional multi-layer effects, Hewlett-Packard was able to realize the intricate flora and animal patterns designed by Tord Boontje on notebook computers (Figure 6). These examples demonstrate the importance of innovating on both product meanings and processing technologies.

In the following, we report two case studies of CMF practices in two large NB manufacturers in Taiwan. By in-depth interviews of CMF professionals and product designers, we document and analyze the role of CMF in NB product development process, contents and sources of CMF database, services provided by CMF professionals, development of new CMF, evaluation of different combinations of CMF, and interaction between designers, engineers and CMF professionals.

Figure 2. HP Mini 110-3500

Figure 3. Asus Eee PC 1015PW

Figure 4. Toshiba Portégé R830

Figure 5. HP TouchSmart TM2-2012TX

Figure 6. HP Mini 110 Tord 3D

CMF CASE STUDY 1

Company A is one of the world’s leading NB manufacturers. Its clients include many well-known 3C brands covering a wide range of consumer electronic products. Since 2007, a few designers have begun to collect and share CMF data out of necessity and interest. As the potentials of a CMF database began to be recognized by the company, a “CMF team” was informally formed in 2009 to take charge of the CMF database, which serves as a reference source to the various business units.

The core person of the CMF team is a senior designer with an industrial design background. The CMF team’s routine tasks include collecting CMF information and regularly publishing reports on CMF trends. From time to time, members of the CMF team might be assigned to support projects at business units—mainly to help define CMF specs. The team could also be called on to make presentations to clients about the CMF technologies that Company A can utilize or have developed.

The CMF database includes annual reports on newest CMF trends from important consumer electronics shows (such as Computex, CeBIT, CES), trend reports published by research service agencies on colors and materials, and CMF sample catalogues. However, the most valuable assets of the CMF database are the physical samples which have been collected over the years from past projects—samples of materials and technologies that are developed either independently by satellite factories, or collaboratively by Company A and satellite factories. The CMF team makes special efforts to collect these physical samples, because many CMF exterior effects result from combining various materials and processing technologies. Without physical samples, designers could not fully understand the effects, nor could they fully capitalize the cutting-edge materials and technologies.

Table 1 shows the schema of Company A’s CMF database. The physical samples concentrate on samples for metal surface treatments and in-mold decoration (IMD) technologies, as dedicated by the needs of design projects.

Table 1. CMF Database Schema for Company A

Finishes	molding	chemical etching
		...
	coating	matte effects
		glossy effects
		colors
		...
	in-mold decoration (IMD)	in-mold rolling (IMR)
		in-mold forming (IMF)
		in-mold bonding (IMB)
		...
	metal surface treatment	brushing
		electroplating
		anodizing
		...
	mylar	screen printing
etching		
...		
Trends	Computex	by year
	CeBIT	by year
	CES	by year
	...	
Supply chain	satellite factory	contacts, profiles, costs, yield rates, etc.
	...	
Others	protective gloves	
	packaging material	
	natural material	
	...	

The CMF team plays the role of an inner consultancy within Company A during product development processes. In addition to providing information on the newest development on CMF, the CMF team also provides information about the supply chains—factories with the capability to produce parts

with the specified CMF, as well as the costs and yield rates from past experience. This knowledge helps designers to make the best decision about CMF, by selecting not just the materials/technologies, but also the supply chain which will realize them. During the interview, a designer mentioned: "An important issue of CMF selection lies in the costs and yield rates. The more we understand CMF technologies, the better we can control the effects and the costs. We are able to select from far more than the materials and techniques we used to know."

CMF CASE STUDY 2

Company B is also one of the world’s leading NB manufacturers. In view of the diminishing profits as a manufacturer, the company has undergone re-organization to elevate the position of design department within the hierarchy, in order to transform from an OEM to an ODM business model.

The CMF Lab was established in 2009 within the Design Center. The lab mainly consists of trend analysis specialists, who update the CMF database based on trend data and augmented with new CMF technologies developed by the company. The lab functions as the information gateway both inside and outside of the company. To the clients, the CMF database build by the lab showcases the company’s capability as an ODM, with deep understanding and control of many CMF applications. To the designers within the company, the CMF lab serves as the library that offers answers to any CMF question.

Main collections of the CMF database are color/material samples purchased from commercial databases. This is complemented by physical product samples and testing samples demonstrating special CMF effects. Table 2 shows the data schema for the CMF database at Company B. The samples in the CMF database is organized according to emotional adjectives (columns), which are in term classified according to colors and materials (rows).

Table 2. CMF Database Schema for Company B

	Soft	Hard	Dynamic	Static
	adjectives e.g.: mild	adjectives e.g.: serious	adjectives e.g.: urban	adjectives e.g.: calm
Colors				
red				
orange				
...				
Materials				
plastic				
metal				
...				

During the interviews, a designer in Company B commented:

"The entire design process is about the definition of CMF - creating values in product design by combining CMF and controlling manufacturing processes."

Company B hopes to gradually build a common language for defining CMF by the establishment of the CMF database.

DISCUSSIONS

We plan to interview several additional major NB manufacturers in the future. Based on the interviews of key personnel in companies A & B, we found that CMF databases can be defined according to the materials and processing, or according to intended messages (emotional adjectives). In either case, the CMF effects are the results from collaborative efforts by the manufacturer and its supply chain. As illustrated in Figure 7, rather than serving as a passive information source, many CMF specialists within a company functions more as an active R&D agent that coordinates the efforts of a network of satellite factories and material providers to develop innovative CMF.

Figure 7. CMF Supply Chain

We found also that innovation in CMF often implies overcoming technology barriers. When a product is deemed too easy to produce, it is often also perceived to be less innovative. Theoretically, high aesthetics achieved through high technologies should create the best CMF effects. However, in reality, costs and yield rates still need to be taken into consideration. A designer commented during our interview:

“We did not select some CMF treatments because of low yield rates or bad durability. Some fancy CMF treatments could not survive two years of usage. Not only does our client try to avoid selection of such CMF, but also us, out of concerns for our reputation.”

For many brand owners, lasting quality in a product is more important than fancy CMF, whose consistency could be difficult to maintain in mass production.

During our interviews, we also found that designers stressed the importance of understanding CMF technologies and processes. When making the decisions about CMF, they must consider the aesthetic effects, as well as costs and yield rates. We therefore suggest that the schema of CMF database begin with two dimensions: materials (such as plastics, metals, and nature materials) and processing (such as printing, coating, and etching). Because several different layers of materials are combined to create the exterior surface of a product,

the colors, materials, and finishes cannot be discussed independently. When defining CMF data, it is important to include processing, finishing, and layering information. The database should allow a designer to examine all possible material/process combinations, enabling the designer to choose the best possible alternative among them.

We found that CMF specialists not only passively distribute commercially available CMF information, but also actively develop unique CMF technologies collaboratively with a company’s supply chain. It is possible to develop innovate CMF by new ways of combining materials, processes, and finishes. As demonstrated by Apple’s series of products using anodized aluminum to establish its brand image, CMF could serve as branding strategy. We hope that findings from this study will serve as a foundation for further research on innovate product design via CMF related technologies.

Table 3. Material-Processes Combination

		material			
		plastic	metal	nature material	...
processes	printing				
	coating				
	etching				
	...				

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